

CURRENT-VOLTAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF AMORPHOUS-SI BASED PLASMONIC SOLAR CELLS WITH PHOTONIC CRYSTAL BACK REFLECTORS

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Abstract:

In order to enhance the absorption in the near *infrared* region for a-Si:H based thin film solar cells various light trapping schemes are proposed in the literature. Use of photonic crystal back reflectors is one such scheme which is proved to be capable of increasing absorption significantly and hence, is very effective to harvest weekly- absorbing, long- wavelength photons. However, there are no analytical models found in the literature to describe the underlying physics of the current-voltage characteristics of these solar cells (commonly referred to as plasmonic solar cells). In this work, therefore, an analytical model of the current-voltage characteristics has been developed for a-Si:H based p-i-n solar cells with photonic crystal back reflectors. The model incorporates the effect of the series resistance using the concept of the perturbation theory. The model results show a significant improvement in the current-voltage characteristics, as expected.

Key words: Thin film solar cell, plasmonic cell, photonic crystal back reflector, Current-voltage characteristics, perturbation theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

The second generation thin film solar cells draw increasing interest of the researchers because of their lower production cost and improved efficiency. Hydrogenated amorphous Si (a-Si:H) absorber based cells are one of the most potential photoconductors for thin film solar cells because of their excellent efficiency [1]. These solar cells use p-i-n type structure where the p and n-layers are few nm and the i-layer is typically less than 500 nm. These cells have problem of weak absorption of photons near the band edge. Since the red and near infrared photons have longer absorption lengths, difficulties arise to absorb these photons in the thin absorber layer.

In order to improve the cell efficiency, light trapping techniques are used. Random textured metallic back reflectors of silver (coated with ZnO) are used in conventional light trapping techniques. Here, the reflector increases the optical path length of long-wavelength photons [2] by scattering the light within

the absorber layer. However, these metallic back reflectors suffer from intrinsic losses from surface plasmon (SP) modes generated at the granular metal-dielectric interface [3]. Another common light trapping scheme is the use of periodic metallic gratings. These are employed to improve absorption in the polymer based thin film solar cells [4], nanocrystalline solar cells [5] and crystalline silicon solar cells [6]. Since photonic crystals are proved to manipulate and guide lights in novel ways [7], Zhou *et al.* [8] developed a light trapping scheme replacing the back reflector by a two-dimensional photonic crystal on top of distributed Bragg reflector (DBR). By diffracting photons through oblique angles in the absorber layer, these photonic crystals increase the path length of photons. Another way of light trapping scheme is the use of metallic photonic crystal (or a plasmonic crystal) [9] instead of using the dielectric photonic crystal [6].

The increased absorption for the long wavelength photons for the solar cells employing any of the above-mentioned light trapping techniques improves the current-voltage characteristics. Unfortunately, there are no models in the literature to investigate the effects on the current-voltage characteristics. This work, therefore, aims to develop an analytical model of current-voltage characteristics based on the device physics so that a thorough investigation, using this model, can be made to study the effects of various parameters on the current-voltage characteristics.

II. ANALYSIS

The net current density of a solar cell can be expressed as

$$J(V) = J_d(V) - J_{ph}(V) \quad (1)$$

where $J_d(V)$ is the dark saturation current density and $J_{ph}(V)$ is the photo-generated current density. Since the heavily-doped n and p-layers are very thin and the intrinsic base (a-Si:H) region is relatively wider, $J_{ph}(V)$ can be approximated as the photo-generated current component in the i-layer only and the voltage-dependent electric field throughout this region can be assumed as constant and can be expressed as

$$E(V) = \frac{V_{bi} - (V - JR_s)}{W_b} \quad (2)$$

where W_b is the width of the depletion region in the CIGS layer. In Ref. [6,7], W_b is calculated assuming the p-n junction as homojunction and a fitting parameter V_0 is used instead of V_{bi} and the voltage drop across the intrinsic layer JR_s is calculated from a measured value of R_s . In this work W_b and V_{bi} is calculated using actual heterojunction structure. Using Equation (2) and following the derivation in Ref. [6, 7], the total photo-generated current J_{ph} for all wavelengths present in the sun spectrum can be calculated.

A. Derivation of Photo-generated Current Density

The photogeneration current in depletion region is the sum of the photogenerated electron current (J_n) and hole current (J_p). Since electric field is the dominant mechanism for current conduction in the depletion region, diffusion component of these currents are negligible. The basic equations required to deduce these drift-dominated currents are:

$$J_n = qn\mu_n E \quad (4)$$

$$J_p = qp\mu_p E \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = \frac{qn}{\tau_n} - qG \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -\frac{qp}{\tau_p} + qG \quad (7)$$

where μ_n (μ_p) is the electron (hole) mobility, τ_n (τ_p) is the electron (hole) lifetime. G is the wavelength-dependent optical generation rate given by

$$G = \alpha(\lambda) \frac{I(\lambda)\lambda}{hc} e^{-\alpha_1(\lambda)W_E} e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} = \alpha(\lambda)G_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} \quad (8)$$

Combining the above equations [Equations (4) and (6) and Equations (5) and (7)] results in first order differential equations of electrons and holes as

$$\frac{dn}{dx} - nM_n = -G_n \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dx} + pM_p = G_p \quad (10)$$

Where $M_n = \frac{1}{E\tau_n\mu_n}$, $G_n = \frac{G}{E\mu_n}$, and $M_p = \frac{1}{E\tau_p\mu_p}$, $G_p = \frac{G}{E\mu_p}$.

Since the hole and electron start drifting immediately after generation i.e. $p(W_E) \approx 0$ and $n(W_E + x_p) \approx 0$, the solutions of the electron and holes are obtained as

$$n(x) = n_0 (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{M_n(x-x_p)^{-\alpha x_p}}) \quad (11)$$

$$p(x) = p_0 (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{-M_p x}) \quad (12)$$

where

$$n_0 = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_n + \alpha)\mu_n E_n}$$

$$p_0 = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_p - \alpha)\mu_p E_p}$$

The photocurrent density for holes and electron drifting correspondingly towards the bottom and top contact can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} J_n(V, \lambda) &= \frac{q\mu_n E}{x_p(V)} \int_{W_E}^{W_E+x_p} n(x) dx \\ &= \frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_n + \alpha)} (J_0 + J_{n1}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_p(V, \lambda) &= \frac{q\mu_p E}{x_p(V)} \int_{W_E}^{W_E+x_p} p(x) dx \\ &= \frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_E}}{(M_p - \alpha)\mu_p E} (J_0 + J_{p1}) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where

$$J_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-\alpha W_E} (1 - e^{-\alpha x_p})$$

$$J_{n1} = \frac{1}{M_n} e^{M_n(W_E - x_p)^{-\alpha x_p}} (1 - e^{M_n x_p})$$

$$J_{p1} = \frac{1}{M_p} e^{-M_p W_E} (e^{-M_p x_p} - 1)$$

The total photogenerated current J_{ph0} at a particular wavelength λ then can be expressed as

$$J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) = J_n(V, \lambda) + J_p(V, \lambda) \quad (15)$$

The total photogenerated current density is obtained by integrating over all incident photon wavelengths of the solar spectra, i.e.,

$$J_{ph}(V) = \int_0^\infty J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) d\lambda \quad (16)$$

B. DERIVATION OF OF JD(V)

Since the recombination current dominates over the diffusion current, the dark current density J_d can be approximated as the forward biased recombination current density in the depletion region and can be expressed as [7]

$$J_d(V) = \frac{qn_i x_p}{2\sqrt{\tau_n \tau_p}} e^{\frac{q(V - JR_s)}{AKT}} \quad (17)$$

where A is the diode ideality factor. In Ref. [7], A is used as a fitting parameter. In this work, the actual value of $A = 2$ is used. Therefore, this work does not need to use any fitting parameters.

C. DERIVATION OF J(V)

From Equations (2) and (17), it is evident that determination of the total current density, J for a given load voltage, V is analytically intractable. However, using the concept of perturbation theory this intractability problem can be resolved. Since J_{ph} can be solved and $J_d \rightarrow 0$ under short circuit condition (i.e. $V=0$), the total current density J under $V = 0$ is approximately equal to J_{ph} . But for $V > 0$, this does not hold. When $V > 0$, J_d is required and hence, in turn, the knowledge of J is required to determine the voltage drop across the series resistance R_s [Equations (2) and (17)]. Using the concept of the perturbation theory, the JR_s at $V = 0$ can be used to determine J at $V = \delta V$. This is justifiable, since the change in $n(x)$ and $p(x)$ compared to N_a is negligible [Equation (3)] and hence, the change in current densities can also be negligible, provided that the change in the voltage is very little i.e. $\delta V \rightarrow 0$.

Therefore, the $n(x)$, $p(x)$ and JR_s at $V = 0$ can be applied to readily determine the J_d and E and hence, the total current density J at $V = \delta V$ using Equations (2) and (17).

The same process can be repeated at the $V = 2\delta V, 3\delta V, 4\delta V, \dots$ where the values of n , p and J are calculated at $V = \delta V, 2\delta V, 3\delta V, \dots$ respectively. As a result, for each δV increment of voltage, J can be analytically determined.

As compared with the conventional numerical models, this approach is advantageous in the sense that it avoids the use of fitting parameters. The proposed approach is computationally more efficient than the numerical approach, since the total current density at any voltage level (V) can be determined only when the same at $V - \delta V$ is known. The number of iterations, therefore, is limited only by the size of δV in the proposed approach.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the effects of photonic crystal backreflectors on the current-voltage (J-V) characteristics of a p-i-n a-Si:H-based plasmonic solar cell using the model developed in this paper and compare these results with that of a solar cell that uses

flat silver reflector of identical structure. The cell structures and the absorption coefficients for these solar cells are taken from [8].

Because of enhanced light-trapping technique, the plasmonic solar cells have higher absorption coefficients in the long wavelength photos than the solar cells which have flat Ag reflector only. Therefore, the probability of absorption of long wavelength photon energy increases for the plasmonic solar cells, which means that these plasmonic solar cells have higher internal quantum efficiency for the long wavelength photons and consequently, have improved J-V characteristics. These expected results are demonstrated in the Figs. 1 to 4.

Fig 1 Theoretical net current density vs. voltage for different absorber width in plasmonic and flat Ag reflector based solar cells

Fig 1 shows the effect of intrinsic layer width (W_i) on the J-V characteristics. From this figure it is evident that with an increase in W_i , J-V curve improves. This trend is due to the fact that as W_i increases the probability of absorption of long wavelength photons increases which results in the increase in the photo-generated carriers. Carrier lifetime has an adverse effect on J-V characteristics, since decrease in lifetime increases the carrier recombination i.e. increases carrier losses, thereby, causing decrease in the photo-generation current. Therefore, degradation in the J-V characteristics has been observed in Fig 2 for the decrease in the electron lifetime and in Fig 3 for the decrease in the hole lifetime. A comparison of the effects of electron lifetime and hole lifetime observed in these figures reveals that electron lifetime has greater impact than that of the hole lifetime. This can be explained as follows. Carriers photo-generated in the intrinsic layer of a p-i-n structure based solar cells are separated by the electric field in this layer; electrons move to n-type base layer (bottom contact) whereas holes move to the p-type emitter layer (top contact). Since most of carriers are generated near the top contact because of the high absorption coefficients of a-Si:H (for both plasmonic and flat Ag reflector based solar cells), electrons have to traverse a wider distance than the hole to reach the

electrode and hence, electrons have to face higher recombination loss i.e. electron transport

IV. CONCLUSION

The effects of photonic crystal back reflectors on the current-voltage characteristics have been thoroughly investigated in this work. In order to envision the effects, the results are also compared with those of a solar cell having flat Ag reflector. Effects of variation of intrinsic layer width, electron transport and hole transport are also demonstrated. It is found that plasmonic solar cells have improved current-voltage characteristics over the flat Ag reflector based solar cell; the increase in the intrinsic layer width increases the photo-generation current and finally, electron transport is much sensitive than the hole transport in a p-i-n structure based solar cells.

Fig 2 Theoretical net current density vs. voltage for electron lifetime in plasmonic and flat Ag reflector based solar cells

Fig 3 Theoretical net current density vs. voltage for hole lifetime in plasmonic and flat Ag reflector based solar cells

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